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Research Article

'SCREENING OF ANTILICE ACTIVITY OF *INDONEESIELLA ECHIOIDES*' AGAINST *PEDICULUS HUMANIS CAPATIS*Umesh Mitte^{*1}, Sayabanna², Ambika³, Somashekar Nandeni⁴, Bhagyawanti K Patil⁵ and
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Abstract:

Head lice are tiny insects that feed on blood from the human scalp. Head lice most often affect children. The insects usually spread through direct transfer from the hair of one person to the hair of another. Problem of head lice is not a big hazard but If your child scratches an itchy scalp due to head lice, it's possible for the skin to break and develop an infection so therefore, In the present study, petroleum ether and methanolic extracts of *Indoneesiella Echioides* were tested against the *pediculus humanus capitis* by a simple filter paper diffusion method.

The methanolic extract showed 96.2% mortality in 30 minutes and 100% mortality in 60 minutes whereas petroleum ether extracts showed 92.6% mortality in 30 minutes and 100% mortality in 60 minutes.

In order to reduce the mortality time, the extracts are mixed with carrier oil like castor oil, coconut oil and olive oil.

The methanolic extract with all the three-carrier oil showed significant reduction in mortality in 30 minutes whereas petroleum ether showed moderate antilice effect. All the results were well compared with benzoyl benzoate (25% w/v) as standard. The results furnishes scientific basis for the traditional use of this plant as antilice application

Keywords: *Indoneesiella Echioides*, Antilice activity, Filter paper diffusion, *Pediculus humanus capitis*

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INTRODUCTION:

Lice have been intimately associated with man since time immemorial. They are most common during times of stress, such as war, famine, or disasters when people do not bathe or wash their clothing regularly¹. Lice inject an irritating saliva into the skin during feeding which causes considerable itching. Severe infestations may lead to scratching, secondary infections, and scarred, hardened, or pigmented skin conditions known as PEDICULOSIS. In many parts of the world, lice also transmit, pathogens causing human diseases.² Therefore it is necessary to do research for a potent and safe antilice drug.

Figure 01: *Pediculus Humanus Capitis*

Although Traditional medicines are less potent in comparison to synthetic drugs in some cases but still these are consider less toxic or having less side effect in contrast to synthetic drugs.³ Therefore Researchers are diverting their mind towards naturopathy because of lot of side effects of modern medicine.⁴ The ultimate norm for any medicine (human made or natural) is their nontoxicity, effectiveness, specificity, stability and potency which is effectively seen in herbal based medicine.^{5,6}

In India people spend so much money to buy the synthetic marketed products to solve the problems of lice. the lack of efficacy of these synthetic products is due to the emergence of resistance by the head Louse and researchers were aimed on the search of new substitutes to synthetic ingredients, such as phytoconstituents obtained from plant sources.⁷

Indoneesiella Echioides one of the Indian plant possesses valuable medicinal properties and it has

studied for activities like antipyretic, anti-inflammatory and in Many wounds and ailments. The leaf juice of *Indoneesiella Echioides* boiled with coconut oil is applied on head to prevent falling and greying of hairs. The plant is still not investigated for anti-lice activity therefore the aim of the study is to investigate the effect of shade dried leaves of *Indoneesiella Echioides* on head Louse⁸.

METHODOLOGY AND RESULT:

Plant material: Fresh plant material of *Indoneesiella Echioides* was collected from the local fields of deccan areas of India. The plant specimen was identified and authenticated by P. V. Prasanna, Incharge Scientist 'F'. Deccan Reginal Centre, Hyderabad – 48, Botanical Survey of India. **(With a Voucher No. MUC 17091)**. Then the plant was washed under tap water to remove debris and dried under shade for 10 days. The dried leaves were size reduced to course powder in a grinder.

Extraction: The coarse powder of *Indoneesiella Echioides* (500 gm) extracted with Petroleum ether and Methanol by soxhlet extraction technique (figure 02).

Figure 02: Extraction by Soxhlet extraction technique.

All the extracts were concentrated using Rotary vacuum evaporator and kept in a desiccator until further studies the color, consistency and percentage yield were observed⁹. (Table 01)

S. No.	Extract	Nature of Extract	Colour	Weight (gm)	% Yield (w/w)
1.	Petroleum Ether (40-60°C)	Semi solid	Brownish Yellow	5.32	1.72
2.	Methanol		Green	30.37	8.79

Table 01: Observation of Percentage yield and colour consistency

Collection of head lice:

Adult *Pediculus Humanus Capitis* were collected from government school children between the age group of 3 to 12 with the approval of the teachers residing near Ram mandir in Gulbarga district. The lice were collected by combing the children's scalp. After combing, the lice were carefully collected from the white sheet paper kept in front of subjects (Childrens) and also removed from the teeth of the comb into plastic boxes. All the subjects had not been treated with any anti-lice products for the preceding two months. (Figure 03)

Figure 03: Collection of Lice.

ANTI LICE ACTIVITY**Filter paper diffusion method:**

Now a days filter paper assays in Petri dishes are common bioassay method to determine the level of topical insecticides resistance in head lice which provides informative and comparable results. Insecticide treated lices are likely able to continue blood feeding and blood injection after the availability of insecticide or the physiology of louse modify subsequent mortality so it was decided to feed head lice with blood meal by placing the lice on the bare lower leg of one of the authors after collection from the host. Microscopic examination was done in the midgut region and confirmed the blood ingestion. Colony of *Pediculus humanus capitis* was collected by combing the hair of 20-25 infected children at the age group of 3-12. Adult lice were placed in small plastic containers (50 ml polypropylene containers containing 1.5 CM human hair tufts). The mouth was covered with nylon mesh (1 strand/mm) to permit ventilation. For this study the hair tufts were coated with test drugs. The activity was carried out at $37^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 5\%$ and $65^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 5\%$ relative humidity in dark room using water as control. In the majority of situations, carrier oil has sufficient suffocating capabilities to make almost any mixture of essential and carrier oil effective in killing lice and possible effectiveness of penetration using lipid-based compounds. So the extract was mixed with the different carrier oils like coconut oil, castor oil and olive oil in the ratio of 10% 20% and 30% and performed the anti-lice activity¹⁰. (Table 02 and 03)

Table: 02: Effects of Petroleum ether extract of *Indoneesiella Echoides* (PEIE) against *Pediculus humanus capitis*

SL. NO	NUMBER OF LICE	TEST DRUG	CONCENTRATION (gm/ml)	AVERAGE MORTALITY % IN 30 MIN	AVERAGE MORTALITY % IN 60 MIN
1	20	Distilled water (control)	-----	-----	-----
2	20	Benzyl benzoate (standard)	10%	64.2%	100%
			20%	98.0%	100%
			30%	99.5%	100%
3	20	PEIE + Coconut oil	10%	45.76%	87.16%
			20%	59.06%	93.05%
			30%	96.16%	99.05%
4	20	PEIE + Castor oil	10%	40.00%	90.44%
			20%	63.14%	93.51%
			30%	96.01%	97.02%
5	20	PEIE + Olive oil	10%	37.52%	94.60%
			20%	76.38%	100%
			30%	90.79%	100%
6	20	PEIE	-----	91.06%	98%

Table: 03: Effects of Methanolic extract of *Indoneesiella Echoides* (MEIE) against *Pediculus humanus capitis*

SL. NO	NUMBER OF LICE	TEST DRUG	CONCENTRATION (gm/ml)	AVERAGE MORTALITY % IN 30 MIN	AVERAGE MORTALITY % IN 60 MIN
1	20	Distilled water (control)	-----	-----	-----
2	20	Benzyl benzoate (standard)	10%	61.2%	100%
			20%	95.30%	100%
			30%	99.50%	100%
3	20	MEIE + Coconut oil	10%	46.12%	94.48%
			20%	56.18%	100%
			30%	96.11%	100%
4	20	MEIE + Castor oil	10%	48.05%	96.50%
			20%	61.15%	100 %
			30%	100%	100 %
5	20	MEIE + Olive oil	10%	40.75%	95.00%
			20%	76.85%	100%
			30%	98.25%	100%
6	20	MEIE	-----	95.80%	100%

The findings were excellent activity of *Andrographis peniculata* against lice which may be due to the presence of sterol and flavonoids¹¹ which may be a conduct for the enhanced penetration and bioavailability of oil components into the body of lice. Hence It is concluded that it can be optimistic that the present work proved *Indoneesiella Echoides* of therapeutic advantage to be a potential phytochemical target in the design of a drug for the treatment against human lice.

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